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D6.1 Pilot Sites Preparation and Transformation V1

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D6.1 Pilots Sites Preparation and Transformation V1

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AI4PP	Artificial Intelligence for Public Policy
API	Application Programming Interface
BaU	Business as Usual
CSV	Comma-separated values
DAEM	DIMOS ATHINAION EPICHEIRISI MICHANOGRAFISIS
DL	Deep Learning
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
HPC	High Performance Computing
HW	Hardware
ID	Identity Document
IT	Information Technology
ML	Machine Learning
NLP	Natural Language Processing
POE	Power Over Ethernet

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REST API	Representational State Transfer Application Programming Interface
SW	Software
SYDIPA	Municipal Police Infringement Management System
VPME	Virtualized Policy Management Environment
WP	Work Package

Abstract

The main goal of the deliverable 6.1 (Pilot Sites Preparation and Transformation) is to provide a report of the preparatory activities that need to be carried out at the five (5) pilots sites in order to ensure their readiness for pilot operations.

Deploying and validating the required hardware and middleware infrastructures is a prerequisite for deploying and operating the project's pilot systems at the 5 pilot sites.

In addition, mobilisation and engagement of local stakeholders (e.g., policy makers, citizens businesses, etc.), as well as proper training for them to engage in the pilot systems and the VPME, is also required in this direction.

Last but not least, the fulfilment of the ethical management activities (e.g., informed consent) based on the methodology provided by the ethical management task in WP9 is also essential to the deployment and operation of the project's pilot systems at the 5 pilot sites.

Executive summary

In the course of the AI4PublicPolicy project, the D6.1 (Pilot Sites Preparation and Transformation), focuses on the necessary activities required for deploying and operating the project's pilot systems at the 5 pilot sites. Furthermore, it addresses the challenges and dependencies that arise during the course of the project.

To successfully achieve its goals and fulfil its mission, the current document provides information on the preparatory activities required for the preparation and transformation of pilot sites. More specifically, it elaborates on the deployment and validation of the necessary hardware and middleware infrastructures to access the Cloud and HPC resources of EOSC/EGI.

In addition, it emphasises the importance of identifying and mobilising local stakeholders by providing them with proper training and material so as they are engaged with the pilot systems.

Lastly, it stresses the importance of the fulfilment of the ethical management responsibilities by using methodologies provided by the project.

As it will be seen below, the pilots' preparation and transformation activities plan differs based on their needs. More specifically, in terms of the HW/SW required for collecting raw data, DAEM, CDG and LIS pilots will not need to deploy any new equipment for gathering raw data. Instead, they will rely on existing apps and hardware (e.g., sensors etc.) that are already in place. On the other hand, NIC and BURGAS pilots are planning to deploy sensors to facilitate the collection of raw data.

To continue, as far as HW/SW to make real time pilot datasets accessible to the implementation teams, the pilots follow this process: the real time data will be stored locally on servers and access will be provided to authorised users. Then, datasets will be provided to the implementation teams both as rest (stored data) and data in motion (streams of data). For all datasets there is stored data available in different formats (e.g. CSV, JSON, GeoJSON etc.), as exported from pilots' databases, while data streams will be accessed via REST APIs that pilots will implement during the implementation phase. Finally both file exports and REST APIs will be hosted on the pilots' cloud and servers that are already deployed as part of the BaU operation and will be available to the AI4PP Data Collection component via the Web configuration interface that it will be provided for the pilot. Finally, regarding the HW/SW necessary to access the VPME in all cases personal computers and dedicated working stations will be used by the Pilots and they will be set ad-hoc or permanently for these purposes at Pilots' premises.

Moreover, regarding the process to make historical pilot datasets accessible to the implementation teams, DAEM provided historical datasets for three different categories of historical data that covered a period of 12 months. In the same direction, the CDG pilot provided historical data for three datasets that can be fetched via Pilot's web service. As for the NIC pilot, the historical data given to the implementation teams they exported from old sensors installed throughout the city and from patrols took place in different areas of the city. To continue, the NIC pilot provided historical data for different datasets that can be also fetched using the respective web services. Lastly, in the case of the BURGAS pilot, the historical data provided is not considered to be useful at least at this stage of the project.

Regarding the legacy systems already in use, in some cases pilots have already in place some legacy systems that may need to be integrated with AI4PP pilot implementation, while others do not have any like it is the case with the CDG pilot. As for the rest of the pilots, DAEM has already in place a system for the management of payments of the imposed fines, while the NIC pilot is implementing a smart city management platform that helps to deliver a wide range of digital services and might need to be integrated to the AI4PP components. Furthermore, the LIS pilot uses a geographical software system that might be a candidate for integration with the AI4PP. Finally, BURGAS pilot has provided us with a series of legacy systems that are already in use and might need integration based on the integration level that the AI4PP will allow for. More specifically, the BURGAS pilot operates a Smart City Platform, which collects data from various devices and

systems. In addition, it uses a system for more efficient water management as well as two other systems for accounting and recording purposes.

As for the stakeholders' identification and training preparation plan, all Pilots have identified and prioritised the stakeholders that will be involved in the projects and they have already some initial ideas on how to mobilise and train them throughout the project. Firstly, the DAEM pilot provided us with a list of main stakeholders consisting of Heads of Departments, City Employees and Workers as well as citizens. In the case of the CDG pilot, plenty stakeholders of Social Services, Local Authorities and other third parties will be involved. However, the level of their involvement will be further defined at the next phase of the project. To continue in the NIC pilot the city's transportation department, the company operating the buses, the smart city platform administration and citizens (including vulnerable groups like elderly citizens and citizens with limited mobility are the main stakeholders. In the same direction, the LIS pilot will engage in the project, Public and Local Authorities, Citizens groups and Associations, Research Centres and Academia as well as Companies and Organisations of the Sector. Finally, in the BURGAS pilot, water and IT Engineers, Municipal and Water Company Administrators and Municipal experts will be engaged.

Last but not least, regarding the completion of the ethical management activities, all pilots provided us with a report of the ethical provisions that are part of the pilot preparation phase. Please note that those pending will be further addressed at later stages of the project.

1 Introduction

1.1 The AI4PublicPolicy Project

AI4PublicPolicy is a joint effort of policy makers and Cloud/AI experts to unveil AI’s potential for automated, transparent and citizen-centric development of public policies. To this end, the project will deliver, validate, demonstrate and promote a novel Open Cloud platform (i.e. AI4PublicPolicy platform) for automated, scalable, transparent and citizen-centric policy management based on unique AI technologies. The AI4PublicPolicy platform will be an Open Virtualized Policy Management Environment (VPME) that will provide fully-fledged policy development/management functionalities based on AI technologies such as Machine Learning (ML), Deep Learning (DL), Natural Language Processing (NLP) and chatbots, while leveraging citizens’ participation and feedback. It will support the entire policy development lifecycle, based on technologies for the extraction, simulation, evaluation and optimization of interoperable and reusable public policies, with emphasis on citizen-centric policies development and optimization through the realisation of citizen-oriented feedback loops. AI4PublicPolicy will complement public policy development functionalities with the ever-important process reengineering and organisation transformation activities towards ensuring the effective transition from legacy policy development models to emerging AI-based policy making.

The AI4PublicPolicy VPME will be integrated with EOSC with a dual objective. First to facilitate access to the Cloud and HPC resources of EOSC/EGI that are required to enable the project’s AI tools, second to boost the sustainability and wider use of the project’s developments. AI4PublicPolicy’s business plan for sustaining, expanding, commercialising the AI tools and the VPME is based on the development of a community of interested and engaged stakeholders (i.e., public authorities and other policy makers) around the project’s platform.

Figure 1: AI4PublicPolicy methodological approach

1.2 Description of WP6

The WP6 is the pilot's work-package that will be devoted to deploying, operating, validating and evaluating the pilot systems with the active engagement of the public authorities of the consortium.

The main objectives are as follow:

- Undertake preparatory activities at the five (5) pilot sites towards their readiness for the pilot operations.
- Customise and deploy the AI4PublicPolicy outcomes in-line with the requirements and needs of the 5 pilot sites.
- Operate and validate the AI4PublicPolicy platform in different use cases and contexts in the 5 pilot sites.
- Evaluate the pilot systems from a technical and a business perspective.

1.3 Structure of the document

This document is comprised of the following chapters:

- Section 1 presents an introduction to the AI4PP project and to the WP6. In addition the methodology used and the structure for the preparation and transformation activities plan are briefly outlined.
- Section 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 present the preparation and transformation activities plans that the DAEM, CDG, NIC, LIS and BURGAS pilots need to carry out in order to ensure their readiness for pilot operations. More specifically, the pilots provide us with more information on the HW/SW that may be needed for raw data collection, for making real-time data pilot datasets accessible to the implementation teams and for accessing the VPME. Additionally, the processes for making historical pilot datasets accessible to the implementation teams are presented as well as the legacy systems that are in place and might need to be integrated with the AI4PP pilot implementations.
- Section 7 concludes the document.
- Section 8 depicts the Public Funding Disclaimer.

1.4 Methodology

This section will briefly outline the approach and the methods used to write this report as well as the rationale that justifies these choices. To begin with, in order to collect the data and information related to pilots' preparation and transformation activities required to ensure pilots' readiness for the implementation phase, we have broken down the work that needs to be done into seven actions assigned to each pilot. At this point it is important to mention that to assign the actions to the pilots, track their progress and keep the necessary documentation, we used the AI4PP project management tool. According to these actions, pilots were requested to provide us with information on the HW/SW needed for raw data collection, for making the real-time pilot datasets accessible to implementation teams, and for accessing the VPME and EOSC/EGI resources. Pilots needed to provide information on the legacy systems already in place and might need integration with the AI4PP implementations as well as to provide us with more details on the processes implemented to make historical data accessible to the implementation teams. In addition, they were tasked with the creation of an initial table with all the stakeholders that will be involved in the project. The final action assigned to them was relevant to the reporting of the ethical management activities required in the course of this project. More information on these actions will be provided in the following sections (see 1.5.1 to 1.5.3 section below).

Moreover, apart from the actions assigned to the pilots, we organised weekly calls with each of them in order to discuss the actions mentioned above as well as other open actions related to the AI4PP project. The weekly calls with pilots took place from mid-January 2022 until February 2022 and they were also recorded in the project management tool mentioned above along with important information and feedback collected during the calls. In this way, we managed being in constant contact with the pilots throughout the development of this report and we were able to follow all the

developments relevant to the transformation and preparation activities that need to be carried out by pilots.

To conclude, we have decided to follow a similar process at the next phases of the project as we are soon planning to organise another bunch of calls with the pilots to keep track of their progress.

1.5 Structure for the Preparation and Transformation Activities Plan

In this section, we provide the general structure for the plan of preparatory activity categories for the pilots. The aim is to provide a common set of guidelines so that we can fill the activity details for each pilot in the next sections.

1.5.1 Pilot infrastructure, data availability and local systems preparation

HW/SW that may be needed for raw data collection

This section will be devoted to the HW/SW necessary for raw data collection (e.g., sensors etc.). As the collection of the raw data is the starting point of any data analysis, it's essential to elaborate on the required pilots' infrastructure to complete this process.

Process to make historical pilot datasets accessible to implementation teams

While in the deliverable (D2.3) pilots were requested to define their datasets, in the course of this action pilots need to provide historical data for each one of the datasets as defined in the D2.3 deliverable, where applicable.

HW/SW to make real-time pilot datasets accessible to implementation teams

With this action the focus is shifted on the HW/SW needed to provide the implementation teams with real-time datasets. More specifically, pilots are requested to provide us with more details on the equipment and infrastructure that will deploy to store data that will be then integrated into AI4PP (e.g. local servers etc.) or to provide APIs that can be used by the project's central data collection systems (see deliverable D2.6, section **Dataset Collection and Management**).

HW/SW for accessing the VPME and EOSC/EGI resources

In this part of the deliverable, we need to elaborate further on the necessary equipment and infrastructure that is needed to access the pilot UI and algorithms via the VPME component (see deliverable D2.6, section VPME) and EOSC/EGI resources. More specifically, pilots are called to inform us about the HW/SW they are planning to use to ensure their access (e.g., dedicated workstations, personal laptops/computers, operational rooms etc.).

Legacy systems that may need to integrate with AI4PP pilot implementations

In addition, pilots need to record all the legacy systems that are already in place and are used and might need to be integrated with the AI4PP pilot implementations, in the course of this project.

1.5.2 Stakeholders' identification and training preparation

In this section, pilots need to create a full list of stakeholders that will participate in the project and record them along with their roles and responsibilities. More specifically, this process entails identifying, mapping and prioritising stakeholders to determine the best practices for effective engagement. Equally important, pilots need to identify and provide us with details related to the training they are planning to offer to the stakeholders throughout the project. To record all the necessary information, pilots were requested to use the following template.

Stakeholder role
<i>The role description of each stakeholder</i>
Early involvement plan ideas
<p>Include:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. details regarding the involvement of the stakeholder with the project outcomes. 2. a plan on how the stakeholders will be informed about the project progress and the details of their involvement.
Training requirements (Need training? Where? When? Who is the trainer?)
<p>Contains a description of the training requirements for each pilot stakeholder. More specifically:</p> <p>Does the stakeholder need training?</p> <p>If yes, then what is the timing and the place of this training?</p> <p>Who will be the trainer?</p>

1.5.3 Ethical management activities completion

All pilots must complete all ethical management provisions as part of the pilot preparation phase. The ethical management activities are specified in the deliverables of WP9. As part of this deliverable, each pilot needs to provide a status report on the fulfilment of the required activities as listed in the table below.

Table 1: Ethical management activities completion

Activity	Deliverable of Reference	Status (Done/Pending)
The beneficiaries must confirm that they have appointed a Data Protection Officer (DPO) and the contact details of the DPO are made available to all data subjects involved in the research.	D9.1	
Before the beginning of data collection activities, an ethics committee opinion/authorisation on the activities, sources and procedures related to data collection and processing must be in place.	D9.2	
A report by the Ethics Board must be submitted as a deliverable.	D9.3	
A report describing the specific challenges and proposed solutions for deploying the piloted technology at a real scale with real data in real life while and in compliance with the project's ethical requirements must be submitted.	D9.4	
Implement anonymisation/pseudonymisation techniques.	D9.5	
Templates of the informed consent/assent forms and information sheets covering the voluntary participation (humans) and data protection issues (in language and terms intelligible to the participants) must be kept on file.	D9.6	
The pilot must list the personal data harvesting tools which will be used and confirm for each of them whether their policies comply with GDPR requirements.	D9.7	
A description of the security measures that will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to personal data or the equipment used for processing must be submitted.	D9.8	
The pilot must evaluate the ethics risks related to the data processing activities of the project. This includes also an opinion if data protection impact assessment should be conducted under art.35 General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679. The risk evaluation and the opinion must be submitted.	D9.9	

2 DAEM Pilot Preparation and Transformation Activities Plan

2.1 Pilot infrastructure, data availability and local systems preparation

2.1.1 HW/SW that may be needed for raw data collection

DAEM pilot will not use any hardware (e.g. sensors) for raw data collection. All datasets that will be available for this pilot (as defined in deliverable D2.3) will be collected using the mobile apps that are used by DAEM and provided by Novoville. If additional datasets will be required in the next phases of the project, then the focus will be to get them from already established data providers and/or open-source pools of data.

2.1.2 Process to make historical pilot datasets accessible to implementation teams

DAEM provided historical data for the following datasets:

- Incident Reports
- Wallet Transactions
- Parking transactions

The number of all historical data sent covered a period of 12 months of the dataset.

Lastly, all these data were sent to the implementation teams in CSV format, and they were fully anonymised and confidential and aligned with the dataset specifications in the D2.3 deliverable.

2.1.3 HW/SW to make real time pilot datasets accessible to implementation teams

In order to make the real-time data available to the implementation teams, the data will be first stored locally on servers and data access will be provided for authorised users. In this way, the data are kept in a central location and are easily accessible through a shared network.

Datasets will be provided to the implementation teams both as rest (stored data) and data in motion (streams of data).

Stored data will be available for all datasets via ad hoc CSV exports from the Novoville app databases.

Data streams will be accessible via REST APIs that Novoville and DAEM will implement during the implementation phase of the project for all specified datasets.

Both file exports and REST APIs will be hosted on the Novoville cloud and server clusters that are already deployed as part of the BaU operation and will be available to the AI4PP Data Collection component via the Web configuration interface that it will be provided for the pilot. For more details on the data collection mechanism see deliverable D2.6, section Dataset Collection and Management.

2.1.4 HW/SW for accessing the VPME and EOSC/EGI resource

In order to access the pilot VPME UI and EOSC/EGI resources, personal computers and working stations located at DAEM premises will be used throughout this project. The details of the workstation setup or the operations rooms that will be set ad-hoc or permanently will be defined during the implementation phase.

2.1.5 Legacy systems that may need to integrate with AI4PP pilot implementations

As far as the legacy systems at DAEM pilot are concerned, it is essential to mention the [SYDIPA](#) system that is the Municipal Police Infringement Management System, implemented by DAEM and it is already in place for managing **the payment of imposed fines**. Even though no use cases or user stories affect this legacy system in their current version the system needs to be mentioned in case new use cases arise during the implementation phase or in case the current user stories may require an additional integration point as part of their functional analysis. If needed, the technical

requirements for the integration between the AI4PP components and the SYDIPA system will be defined during the implementation phase and will be included in the pilot deliverables (D6.3/D6.4) and the next version of this deliverable, D6.2.

2.2 Stakeholders' identification and training preparation

The list of DAEM pilot stakeholders along with their early involvement and training planning is described in the following sections.

Stakeholder role
<i>Head of Urban Planning Department/Road Construction Sewerage and Public Spaces Management Department Urban Green Spaces and Public Lighting Department.</i>
Early involvement plan ideas
<p>The Heads of these departments that will serve simultaneously as end users and as experts with deep knowledge and expertise, will contribute to the efficient development of the AI4PP tools, by providing constructive input and requirements on the tools as well by providing data and information related to the City's processes and resources.</p> <p>These stakeholders have been involved early by being present to the co-creation sessions that have been organised by the DAEM pilot and via project dissemination activities.</p>
Training requirements (Need training? Where? When? Who is the trainer?)
<p>Training is required for the Heads of these Departments. The timing depends on the availability of the material. The training will take place either at DAEM's or NOVO's premises and it could be given by NOVO and DAEM project partners as well as other experts that could address any technical aspects.</p>

Stakeholder role
<i>City employees of Urban Planning/Road Construction Department Sewerage and Public Spaces Management/Urban Green Spaces Public Lightings Departments.</i>
Early involvement plan ideas
<p>City employees will contribute to the further development of the AI4PP tools, by providing valuable feedback and suggestions for further improvement. In addition, with their expertise in City's services they will provide useful information about the current processes.</p> <p>These stakeholders have been involved early by being present to the co-creation sessions that have been organised by the DAEM pilot and via project dissemination activities.</p>
Training requirements (Need training? Where? When? Who is the trainer?)
<p>Training is required for all of the above categories. The timing depends on the availability of the material. The training will take place either at DAEM's or NOVO's premises and it could be given by NOVO and DAEM project partners as well as other experts that could address any technical aspects.</p>

Stakeholder role
<i>Head of Municipal police</i>
Early involvement plan ideas
<p>The Head of the Municipal Police as an expert in City's mobility planning as well as an end-user of the tools will help to a high degree by informing us about the current processes and by giving us feedback on how well the AI4PP tools meet the department's needs.</p>
Training requirements (Need training? Where? When? Who is the trainer?)
<p>Training is required. The timing depends on the availability of the material. The training could take place either at DAEM's or NOVO's premises and it could be given by NOVO and DAEM project partners as well as other experts that could address any technical issues that arise and further explore the results.</p>

Stakeholder role
<i>City workers, Municipal Policemen</i>
Early involvement plan ideas
City workers and policemen will contribute to the further development of the AI4PP tools, by providing valuable feedback and suggestions for further improvement. In addition, with their experience in City's services they will provide useful information about the current processes.
Training requirements (Need training? Where? When? Who is the trainer?)
Training is required. The timing depends on the availability of the material. The training could take place either at DAEM's or NOVO's premises and it could be given by NOVO and DAEM project partners as well as other experts that could address any technical issues that arise and further explore the results.

Stakeholder role
<i>Citizens Citizen drivers</i>
Early involvement plan ideas
Both these categories will contribute to further improvement of the AI4PP tools by providing valuable feedback on how the outcomes of these tools correspond to their needs. These stakeholders have been involved early by being present to the co-creation sessions that have been organised by the DAEM pilot and via project dissemination activities.
Training requirements (Need training? Where? When? Who is the trainer?)
No training is required.

2.3 Ethical management activities completion

All pilots must complete all ethical management provisions as part of the pilot preparation phase. The ethical management activities are specified in the deliverables of WP9. DAEM status report on the fulfilment of the required activities is listed in the table below.

Table 2: Ethical management activities completion of DAEM pilot

Activity	Deliverable of Reference	Status (Done/Pending)
The beneficiaries must confirm that they have appointed a Data Protection Officer (DPO) and the contact details of the DPO are made available to all data subjects involved in the research.	D9.1	Done
Before the beginning of data collection activities, an ethics committee opinion/authorisation on the activities, sources and procedures related to data collection and processing must be in place.	D9.2	Pending
A report by the Ethics Board must be submitted as a deliverable.	D9.3	Pending
A report describing the specific challenges and proposed solutions for deploying the piloted technology at a real scale with real data in real life while and in compliance with the project's ethical requirements must be submitted.	D9.4	Pending/Deliverable due M36
Implement anonymisation/pseudonymisation techniques.	D9.5	Done
Templates of the informed consent/assent forms and information sheets covering the voluntary participation (humans) and data protection issues (in language and terms intelligible to the participants) must be kept on file.	D9.6	Done
The pilot must list the personal data harvesting tools which will be used and confirm for each of them whether their policies comply with GDPR requirements.	D9.7	Done
A description of the security measures that will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to personal data or the equipment used for processing must be submitted.	D9.8	Done
The pilot must evaluate the ethics risks related to the data processing activities of the project. This includes also an opinion if data protection impact assessment should be conducted under art.35 General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679. The risk evaluation and the opinion must be submitted.	D9.9	Done

3 CDG Pilot Preparation and Transformation Activities Plan

3.1 Pilot infrastructure, data availability and local systems preparation

3.1.1 HW/SW that may be needed for raw data collection

In terms of HW/SW required for raw data, the CDG pilot will not use any HW/SW like sensors, for gathering raw data. All datasets that will be available for this pilot (as defined in deliverable D2.3) will be collected using the web apps and other manual or semi-manual collection mechanisms that are used by CDG. If additional datasets will be required in the next phases of the project then the focus will be to get them from already established data providers.

3.1.2 Process to make historical pilot datasets accessible to implementation teams

Historical data are available in CSV and GeoJSON formats for 3 of the CDG datasets:

- Data set on the location of Genoa's Municipality polling places.
- Data set on the Genoa's Municipality polling place corresponds to the citizen's address (building).
- Data set on Genoa Municipality territorial perimeter of voting sections.

Historical data for these datasets can be fetched using the <https://mappe.comune.genova.it> web service. The actual endpoints for these historical data are specified in deliverable D2.3.

For the rest of the datasets the historical data will be available during the implementation phase and will be recorded as part of D6.2 and D6.5 deliverables.

3.1.3 HW/SW to make real time pilot datasets accessible to implementation teams

In order to make the real-time data available to the implementation teams, the data will be first stored locally on servers and data access will be provided for authorised users. In this way, the data are kept in a central location and are easily accessible through a shared network.

Datasets will be provided to the implementation teams both as rest (stored data) and data in motion (streams of data).

Stored data will be available for all datasets via ad hoc CSV exports.

Data streams will be accessible via REST APIs like <https://mappe.comune.genova.it> and other web services that will be implemented during the implementation phase of the project for all specified datasets.

Both file exports and REST APIs will be hosted on CDG server clusters that are already deployed as part of the BaU operation and will be available to the AI4PP Data Collection component via the Web configuration interface that it will provide for the pilot. For more details on the data collection mechanism see deliverable D2.6, section Dataset Collection and Management.

3.1.4 HW/SW for accessing the VPME and EOSC/EGI resource

In order to access the pilot VPME UI and EOSC/EGI resources, personal computers and working stations located at CDG premises will be used throughout this project. Workstations and operations rooms that will be needed will be set ad-hoc or permanently during the implementation phase.

3.1.5 Legacy systems that may need to integrate with AI4PP pilot implementations

For the time being, there aren't any legacy systems in place in the CDG pilot that need to be integrated with the AIPP pilot implementations.

3.2 Stakeholders' identification and training preparation

The list of CDG pilot stakeholders along with their early involvement and training planning is described in the following sections.

Stakeholder role
<i>Directorate/Social services Directors - Smart City Social Services department and related offices (adults' area, elderly people area, minors' area, disabled people area, migrants' area) Territorial Social Services offices</i>
Early involvement plan ideas
These stakeholders have been involved early by being present to the co-creation sessions that have been organised by CDG pilot and via project dissemination activities.
Training requirements (Need training? Where? When? Who is the trainer?)
Training is required. Time and place to be defined when training material is available.

Stakeholder role
<i>Citizens Schools Third Sector Organisations Professional Associations Councils Legal Authorities Police Town Halls and Directors Region Institution Ministries Politicians National Statistical Institutes Health Care Institution Social Welfare Territorial Associations</i>
Early involvement ideas
Their involvement will be defined at later stages of the project. Currently can be included in project dissemination efforts.
Training requirements (Need training? Where? When? Who is the trainer?)
No training is required.

Stakeholder role
<i>Returning officers and polling station staff Polling stations staging staff Staff management Public Administration and General Director Technical office Registry office Supply office Toponymy office</i>

Early involvement ideas
These stakeholders have been involved early by being present to the co-creation sessions that have been organised by CDG pilot and via project dissemination activities.
Training requirements (Need training? Where? When? Who is the trainer?)
Training is required. Time and place to be defined when training material is available.

Stakeholder role
Law enforcements Local police Civil protection Non-educational locations Citizens <i>School System</i> <i>Town halls</i>
Early involvement ideas
Their involvement will be defined at a later stage of the project.
Training requirements (Need training? Where? When? Who is the trainer?)
No training required.

3.3 Ethical management activities completion

All pilots must complete all ethical management provisions as part of the pilot preparation phase. The ethical management activities are specified in the deliverables of WP9. CDG status report on the fulfilment of the required activities is listed in the table below.

Table 3: Ethical management activities completion of CDG pilot

Activity	Deliverable of Reference	Status (Done/Pending)
The beneficiaries must confirm that they have appointed a Data Protection Officer (DPO) and the contact details of the DPO are made available to all data subjects involved in the research.	D9.1	Done
Before the beginning of data collection activities, an ethics committee opinion/authorisation on the activities, sources and procedures related to data collection and processing must be in place.	D9.2	Pending
A report by the Ethics Board must be submitted as a deliverable.	D9.3	Pending
A report describing the specific challenges and proposed solutions for deploying the piloted technology at a real scale with real data in real life while and in compliance with the project's ethical requirements must be submitted.	D9.4	Pending/Deliverable due M36

Implement anonymisation/pseudonymisation techniques.	D9.5	Done
Templates of the informed consent/assent forms and information sheets covering the voluntary participation (humans) and data protection issues (in language and terms intelligible to the participants) must be kept on file.	D9.6	Done
The pilot must list the personal data harvesting tools which will be used and confirm for each of them whether their policies comply with GDPR requirements.	D9.7	Done
A description of the security measures that will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to personal data or the equipment used for processing must be submitted.	D9.8	Done
The pilot must evaluate the ethics risks related to the data processing activities of the project. This includes also an opinion if data protection impact assessment should be conducted under art.35 General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679. The risk evaluation and the opinion must be submitted.	D9.9	Done

4 NIC Pilot Preparation and Transformation Activities Plan

4.1 Pilot infrastructure, data availability and local systems preparation

4.1.1 HW/SW that may be needed for raw data collection

The NIC pilot will rely on sensors integrated in the smart city platform, (including sensors for traffic information detection, parking spaces information, air quality measurements and noise level measurements), as well as sensors of the bus operation company. For the inclusiveness functionalities of the pilot (e.g., policies for inclusiveness zones) that pilot will also exploit noise datasets and reports available in the city to help to better gauge the level of noise in different areas.

The pilot may also benefit from any additional sensor integration in the Nicosia smart city platform that will take place during the project.

4.1.2 Process to make historical pilot datasets accessible to implementation teams

The NIC pilot has some historical datasets at its disposal: the first set derived from sensors that were installed around the city and collected by the Nicosia Smart City Platform. Apart from that, the other set of historical datasets are acquired from the population census, from the Cyprus Public Transport company, and from patrols containing information regarding the background noise in a specific area.

The following are the first historical datasets provided to the implementation teams:

- Buses data (calendar, routes, trips, stops)
- Traffic Analysis data
- Smart Parking sensors data
- Environmental sensors data
- Noise Auditing Patrols data

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As for the format of this data, they have been stored in CSV, JSON and Excel files to be made available to the implementation teams. The files have been shared with the development team using the project file repository.

Last but not least, it should be also mentioned that for the purposes of the project no personal data will be shared, as the data were fully anonymised and confidential and aligned with the dataset specifications in the D2.3 deliverable.

4.1.3 HW/SW to make real time pilot datasets accessible to implementation teams

In order to make the real-time data available to the implementation teams, the data will be first stored locally on servers and data access will be provided for authorised users. In this way, the data are kept in a central location and are easily accessible through a shared network.

Datasets will be provided to the implementation teams both as rest (stored data) and data in motion (streams of data).

Stored data will be available for all datasets via ad hoc CSV exports, JSON and Excel files. Data streams will be accessible via REST APIs that will be implemented by Unparallel, sensor vendors and NIC technical teams during the implementation phase of the project for all specified datasets.

Both file exports and REST APIs will be hosted on Nicosia server clusters that are already deployed as part of the BaU operation or will be deployed as part of the sensor installation activities and will be available to the AI4PP Data Collection component via the Web configuration interface that it will provide for the pilot. For more details on the data collection mechanism see deliverable D2.6, section Dataset Collection and Management.

4.1.4 HW/SW for accessing the VPME and EOSC/EGI resource

In order to access the pilot VPME UI platform and EOSC/EGI resources, personal computers and working stations located at NIC premises will be used throughout this project.

4.1.5 Legacy systems that may need to integrate with AI4PP pilot implementations

When it comes to legacy systems, NIC pilot has selected **Nokia** to deliver the **smart city management platform** for Nicosia to help advance the municipality of Nicosia's smart city transformation.

Overall, this platform will help city authorities to deliver a range of new digital services that include urban mobility, smart parking, intelligent street lighting, environmental sensors, sustainable waste management, digital signage, and information services. As the platform brings powerful levels of integration capability, we can consider it as a candidate for future integration with the AI4PP components.

If new use cases are identified during the implementation phase that require integration with the Nicosia Smart City platform, then their feasibility and development will be discussed ad-hoc during the implementation phase given the capabilities and the flexibility that the AI4PP technical components will provide. Any new development at this front will be included in deliverables D6.2, D6.7 and D6.8.

4.2 Stakeholders' identification and training preparation

The list of NIC pilot stakeholders along with their early involvement and training planning is described in the following sections.

Stakeholder role
<i>Municipality/Public Health Department/ Digital Transformation and Smart City Department</i>
Early involvement plan ideas
Employees of the Municipality, the Smart City Office and Noise Management Services will

<p>contribute by providing feedback on the current processes in place in order to address mobility, and environmental data, including suggestions for improvement of the different situations. In addition, as end- users they could also give feedback on the effectiveness of the AI4PP tools produced.</p>
<p>Training requirements (Need training? Where? When? Who is the trainer?)</p>
<p>Training is required. The timing depends on the availability of the material. The training could take place at NIC premises. The training could be given by NIC project partners as well as other experts that could address any technical issues that arise.</p>

<p>Stakeholder role</p>
<p><i>Citizens</i></p>
<p>Early involvement plan ideas</p>
<p>Citizens will have a strong involvement in the policy development and evaluation by participating in the co-creation activities and providing valuable feedback. Additionally, they will be engaged in the development, evaluation and validation of the VPME tools by providing input that will be taken into account and will drive the future development. Overall, they will be engaged in the designing and implementation of the NIC pilot.</p>
<p>Training requirements (Need training? Where? When? Who is the trainer?)</p>
<p>No training is required.</p>

<p>Stakeholder role</p>
<p><i>Research Centres and Academia</i></p>
<p>Early involvement plan ideas</p>
<p>They will be involved in the evaluation of the output of AI4PP as well as provide suggestions for other tools that can facilitate the dissemination of the results.</p>
<p>Training requirements (Need training? Where? When? Who is the trainer?)</p>
<p>No training is required.</p>

<p>Stakeholder role</p>
<p><i>Cyprus Public Transport</i></p>
<p>Early involvement plan ideas</p>
<p>Cyprus Public Transport provides the information regarding the routes of the buses as well as bus stops. As they arrange the bus routes they are involved as needed to provide early feedback and valuable input on the tools and policies produced by the AI4PP project.</p>
<p>Training requirements (Need training? Where? When? Who is the trainer?)</p>

No training is required.

4.3 Ethical management activities completion

All pilots must complete all ethical management provisions as part of the pilot preparation phase. The ethical management activities are specified in the deliverables of WP9. NIC status report on the fulfilment of the required activities is listed in the table below.

Table 4: Ethical management activities completion of NIC pilot

Activity	Deliverable of Reference	Status
The beneficiaries must confirm that they have appointed a Data Protection Officer (DPO) and the contact details of the DPO are made available to all data subjects involved in the research.	D9.1	Done
Before the beginning of data collection activities, an ethics committee opinion/authorisation on the activities, sources and procedures related to data collection and processing must be in place.	D9.2	Pending
A report by the Ethics Board must be submitted as a deliverable.	D9.3	Pending
A report describing the specific challenges and proposed solutions for deploying the piloted technology at a real scale with real data in real life while and in compliance with the project's ethical requirements must be submitted.	D9.4	Pending/Deliverable due M36
Implement anonymisation/pseudonymisation techniques.	D9.5	Done
Templates of the informed consent/assent forms and information sheets covering the voluntary participation (humans) and data protection issues (in language and terms intelligible to the participants) must be kept on file.	D9.6	Done
The pilot must list the personal data harvesting tools which will be used and confirm for each of them whether their policies comply with GDPR requirements.	D9.7	Done
A description of the security measures that will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to personal data or the equipment used for processing must be submitted.	D9.8	Done
The pilot must evaluate the ethics risks related to the data processing activities of the project. This includes also an opinion if data protection impact assessment should be conducted under art.35 General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679. The risk evaluation and the opinion must be submitted.	D9.9	Done

5 LIS Pilot Preparation and Transformation Activities Plan

5.1 Pilot infrastructure, data availability and local systems preparation

5.1.1 HW/SW that may be needed for raw data collection

In terms of HW/SW required for raw data, the LIS pilot will not use any new type of sensors or other data collection equipment apart from the already deployed ones, for gathering raw data. All datasets that will be available for this pilot (as defined in deliverable D2.3) will be collected using existing methods.

5.1.2 Process to make historical pilot datasets accessible to implementation teams

Historical data are available for the following LIS datasets:

1. Identification and location of the air quality and meteorology sensors
2. Historical data of the records measured for all parameters
3. Lisbon green structure
4. Lisbon Cycling network
5. Lisbon main road network
6. Lisbon secondary road network
7. Data on the number and type of buildings and demographics

The historical data for the above datasets are fetched using the following web services:

1. <http://dados.cm-lisboa.pt>
2. <http://opendata-cml.gart.pt>
3. <https://services.arcgis.com>
4. <https://opendata.arcgis.com/>
5. <http://mapas.ine.pt>
6. <https://api.ipma.pt>

The available formats for historical data are JSON, GeoJSON and CSV.

The actual endpoints for these historical data are specified in deliverable D2.3. For the rest of the datasets the historical data will be available during the implementation phase and will be recorded as part of D6.2 and D6.9 deliverables.

5.1.3 HW/SW to make real time pilot datasets accessible to implementation teams

In order to make the real-time data available to the implementation teams, the data will be first stored locally on servers and data access will be provided for authorised users. In this way, the data are kept in a central location and are easily accessible through a shared network.

Datasets will be provided to the implementation teams both as rest (stored data) and data in motion (streams of data).

Stored data will be available for all datasets via ad hoc CSV exports.

Data streams will be accessible via APIs and file transfer endpoints using the following web services:

1. <http://dados.cm-lisboa.pt>
2. <http://opendata-cml.gart.pt>
3. <https://services.arcgis.com>
4. <https://opendata.arcgis.com/>
5. <http://mapas.ine.pt>
6. <https://api.ipma.pt>

Both file exports and REST APIs will be hosted on server clusters that are already deployed as part of the BaU operation and will be available to the AI4PP Data Collection component via the Web configuration interface that it will provide for the pilot. For more details on the data collection mechanism see deliverable D2.6, section Dataset Collection and Management.

5.1.4 HW/SW for accessing the VPME and EOSC/EGI resource

In this section more details will be given on the HS/SW Lisboa E-Nova will be used for accessing the VPME UI and EOSC/EGI resources. At this stage of the project, they have at their disposal a couple of dedicated computers used for running simulations. Thus, the plan is to use these working stations guaranteeing access to UI and algorithms on EOSC cloud.

5.1.5 Legacy systems that may need to integrate with AI4PP pilot implementations.

LIS considers the municipality geographical software system (ArcGIS) that is used for building maps as an integration system candidate for AI4PP components.

However no further technical details or integration specs have been provided for this integration. If new use cases are identified during the implementation phase that require integration with the ArcGIS platform then their feasibility and development will be discussed ad-hoc during the implementation phase given the capabilities and the flexibility that the AI4PP technical components will provide. Any new development at this front will be included in deliverables D6.2, D6.9 and D6.10.

5.2 Stakeholders’ identification and training preparation

The list of LIS pilot stakeholders along with their early involvement and training planning is described in the following sections.

Stakeholder role
<i>Public and Local Authorities</i>
Early involvement plan ideas
<p>End-users/Data providers</p> <p>Authorities will help to shape the AI4PP tools goals, functionalities and layouts, and the ambition of the tools based on the data availability. At a later stage, they will return to the AI4PP tools to inform their energy policy- and decision-making rationale.</p> <p>These stakeholders have been involved early by being present to the co-creation sessions that have been organised by LIS pilot and via project dissemination activities.</p>
Training requirements (Need training? Where? When? Who is the trainer?)
<p>Training is needed. The training will be held either at the Public and Local authorities’ premises or at Lisboa E-Nova or remotely. The timing depends on the availability of the material. The training will be given by Lisboa E-Nova and by project partners, proficient in programming language to elaborate on eventual technical aspects and further exploitation of results.</p>

Stakeholder role
<i>Citizens groups and associations</i>
Early involvement plan ideas
<p>Beneficiaries</p> <p>The “leaders” have the potential to mobilise their networks, to promote energy literacy and capacitation, and to motivate discussions on the efficacy of local AI-based energy policy making.</p>

<p>Citizens will provide input to fine-tuning the AI4PP tools, by voicing on to what level the decisions based on the tools are answering their needs.</p> <p>These stakeholders have been involved early by being present to the co-creation sessions that have been organised by LIS pilot and via project dissemination activities.</p>
<p>Training requirements (Need training? Where? When? Who is the trainer?)</p>
<p>Only the “leaders” might need training. The training will be held either at the Public and Local authorities’ premises or at Lisboa E-Nova or remotely. The timing depends on the availability of the material. Lisboa E-Nova is the trainer.</p>

<p>Stakeholder role</p>
<p><i>Research Centres and Academia</i></p>
<p>Early involvement plan ideas</p>
<p>Expertise</p> <p>Building on the science that has been produced, state-of-the-art methods and innovative products and services, the early stages of the AI4PP tools’ development will encompass work sessions with the local experts on AI, ML and big data.</p> <p>These stakeholders have been involved early by being present to the co-creation sessions that have been organised by LIS pilot and via project dissemination activities.</p>
<p>Training requirements (Need training? Where? When? Who is the trainer?)</p>
<p>Training is not expected at this stage.</p>

<p>Stakeholder role</p>
<p><i>Companies and Organisations of the sector</i></p>
<p>Early involvement plan ideas</p>
<p>Business opportunities</p> <p>Leveraged on the AI-based policy making, new synergies and business models, and large-scale sustainable investments, can potentially be created that help to achieve the energy and climate goals of the city.</p>
<p>Training requirements (Need training? Where? When? Who is the trainer?)</p>
<p>Training is not expected at this stage</p>

5.3 Ethical management activities completion

All pilots must complete all ethical management provisions as part of the pilot preparation phase. The ethical management activities are specified in the deliverables of WP9. LIS status report on the fulfilment of the required activities as listed in the table below.

Table 5: Ethical management activities completion of LIS pilot

Activity	Deliverable of Reference	Status
The beneficiaries must confirm that they have appointed a Data Protection Officer (DPO) and the contact details of the DPO are made available to all data subjects involved in the research.	D9.1	Done
Before the beginning of data collection activities, an ethics committee opinion/authorisation on the activities, sources and procedures related to data collection and processing must be in place.	D9.2	Pending
A report by the Ethics Board must be submitted as a deliverable.	D9.3	Pending
A report describing the specific challenges and proposed solutions for deploying the piloted technology at a real scale with real data in real life while and in compliance with the project's ethical requirements must be submitted.	D9.4	Pending/Deliverable due M36
Implement anonymisation/pseudonymisation techniques.	D9.5	Done
Templates of the informed consent/assent forms and information sheets covering the voluntary participation (humans) and data protection issues (in language and terms intelligible to the participants) must be kept on file.	D9.6	Done
The pilot must list the personal data harvesting tools which will be used and confirm for each of them whether their policies comply with GDPR requirements.	D9.7	Done
A description of the security measures that will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to personal data or the equipment used for processing must be submitted.	D9.8	Done
The pilot must evaluate the ethics risks related to the data processing activities of the project. This includes also an opinion if data protection impact assessment should be conducted under art.35 General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679. The risk evaluation and the opinion must be submitted.	D9.9	Done

6 BURGAS Pilot Preparation and Transformation Activities Plan

6.1 Pilot infrastructure, data availability and local systems preparation

6.1.1 HW/SW that may be needed for raw data collection

BURGAS pilot will use a network of water pipes sensors that will be installed in various locations in order to collect raw measurements and data.

The sensor network is currently under development and testing by EKSO partner and is planned to be deployed early in the implementation phase of the project.

More sensor and installation technical details will be included in the deliverables D6.2 and D6.11

6.1.2 Process to make historical pilot datasets accessible to implementation teams

BURGAS pilot had already provided historical data related to various measurements like water flow rate, water pressure, number of accidents, water losses etc. However, the historical data do not seem to be useful for the implementation teams at least for this stage of the project. As a result, we need to start working with real data, when the new EKSO sensor network is deployed.

6.1.3 HW/SW to make real time pilot datasets accessible to implementation teams

In order to make the real-time data available to the implementation teams, the data will be first stored locally on servers and data access will be provided for authorised users. In this way, the data are kept in a central location and are easily accessible through a shared network.

Datasets will be provided to the implementation teams both as rest (stored data) and data in motion (streams of data).

Stored data will be available for all datasets via ad hoc CSV exports from the EKSO databases.

Data streams will be accessible via APIs that will be implemented by EKSO and BURGAS technical teams during the implementation phase of the project for all specified datasets.

Both file exports and APIs will be hosted on EKSO server clusters that will be set up as part of the sensor installation activities and will be available to the AI4PP Data Collection component via the Web configuration interface that it will provide for the pilot. For more details on the data collection mechanism see deliverable D2.6, section Dataset Collection and Management.

6.1.4 HW/SW for accessing the VPME and EOSC/EGI resource

In terms of the HW/SW, BURGAS pilot is planning to access the VPME UI and EOSC/EGI resources using workstations and internet connections that currently exist in BURGAS Municipality and the Water Utility Company. The VPME access control system will need to be aligned with the BURGAS Municipality access policies during the implementation phase. Further details on the access setup will be included in the deliverables D6.2 and D6.11.

6.1.5 Legacy systems that may need to integrate with AI4PP pilot implementations

BURGAS pilot has already in place a set of legacy systems that are candidates for integration with the AI4PP pilot components. These systems are described below:

- **Smart city platform** (smartburgas.eu): Municipality of BURGAS operates a smart city platform that acts as a digital brain of the city and collects data from various smart devices and systems operating in the urban environment.
- **Plasment** is a system in use that helps in registering the water supply and sewerage accidents, the number of water metres, the number of subscribers as well as the collected water quantities.
- **SioPro** and the **Archimed**, systems used for accounting purposes and record keeping.

However no further technical details or integration specs have been provided regarding the integration with the above systems. If new use cases are identified during the implementation phase that require information exchange between the AI4PP components and one or more of the above platforms, then the technical feasibility will be discussed ad-hoc during the implementation phase given the capabilities and the flexibility that the AI4PP technical components will provide. Any new development at this front will be included in deliverables D6.2, D6.11 and D6.12.

6.2 Stakeholders' identification and training preparation

The list of BURGAS pilot stakeholders along with their early involvement and training planning is described in the following sections.

Stakeholder role
<i>Water Utility Company Administrator</i>
Early involvement plan ideas
<p>They will have full access to the pilot interface and will use it to solve issues. They will also be able to give the necessary authorization to engineers from the Water Utility Company to access the system on an as-needed basis. Lastly, they will oversee the use of the platform.</p> <p>These stakeholders have been involved early by being present to the co-creation sessions that have been organised by BURGAS pilot and via project dissemination activities.</p>
Training requirements (Need training? Where? When? Who is the trainer?)
<p>They will need training related to the functionality of the platform. The training will probably be held online by the developers of the platform. Regarding the timing of the training, this depends on the availability of the material.</p>

Stakeholder role
<i>Municipal Administrator of the system</i>
Early involvement plan ideas
<p>Municipal Administrations of the System They will be responsible for controlling the access granted to the municipal experts to the system.</p> <p>These stakeholders have been involved early by being present to the co-creation sessions that have been organised by BURGAS pilot and via project dissemination activities.</p>
Training requirements (Need training? Where? When? Who is the trainer?)
<p>They will need training related to the functionality of the platform. The training will probably be held online by the developers of the platform. Regarding the timing of the training, this depends on the availability of the material.</p>

Stakeholder role
<i>Municipal Experts (not part of the project)</i>
Early involvement plan ideas
<p>They are interested in the work in progress of the other pilots. While the project is ongoing, their access rights will be limited due to the privacy/security issues. Once the project is completed, they will have the full access rights that are normally granted to experts from BURGAS Municipality. To use the site, they need to complete a registration to have access to the site's information.</p> <p>These stakeholders have been involved early by being present to the co-creation sessions that have been organised by the BURGAS pilot and via project dissemination activities.</p>
Training requirements (Need training? Where? When? Who is the trainer?)

They will need training and further instructions related to data security and data sharing.
Stakeholder role
<i>Municipal Experts (part of the project)</i>
Early involvement plan ideas
They will have full user access during and after the implementation of the project. They will be provided with login access by the administrators. These stakeholders have been involved early by being present to the co-creation sessions that have been organised by the BURGAS pilot and via project dissemination activities.
Training requirements (Need training? Where? When? Who is the trainer?)
They will need training related to the functionality of the platform. The training will probably be held online by the developers of the platform. Regarding the timing of the training, this depends on the availability of the material.

Stakeholder Role
<i>Water Engineers</i>
Early involvement plan ideas
They are the main users of the system for their day-to-day work. These stakeholders have been involved early by being present to the co-creation sessions that have been organised by the BURGAS pilot and via project dissemination activities.
Training requirements (Need training? Where? When? Who is the trainer?)
They need training that will take place locally.

Stakeholder Role
<i>Third parties interested in the project</i>
Early involvement plan ideas
Access to the marketplace will be given to them, with or without registration. The platform must have an interface in Bulgarian, at least for the BURGAS pilot.
Training requirements (Need training? Where? When? Who is the trainer?)
In terms of training, they will only need user instructions.

Stakeholder Role
IT Engineers

Early involvement plan ideas
Will integrate local systems with the AI4PP platform.
Training requirements (Need training? Where? When? Who is the trainer?)
Training is not required.

6.3 Ethical management activities completion

All pilots must complete all ethical management provisions as part of the pilot preparation phase. The ethical management activities are specified in the deliverables of WP9. BURGAS status report on the fulfilment of the required activities is listed in the table below.

Table 6: Ethical management activities completion of BURGAS pilot

Activity	Deliverable of Reference	Status
The beneficiaries must confirm that they have appointed a Data Protection Officer (DPO) and the contact details of the DPO are made available to all data subjects involved in the research.	D9.1	Done
Before the beginning of data collection activities, an ethics committee opinion/authorisation on the activities, sources and procedures related to data collection and processing must be in place.	D9.2	Pending
A report by the Ethics Board must be submitted as a deliverable.	D9.3	Pending
A report describing the specific challenges and proposed solutions for deploying the piloted technology at a real scale with real data in real life while and in compliance with the project's ethical requirements must be submitted.	D9.4	Pending/Deliverable due M36
Implement anonymisation/pseudonymisation techniques.	D9.5	Done
Templates of the informed consent/assent forms and information sheets covering the voluntary participation (humans) and data protection issues (in language and terms intelligible to the participants) must be kept on file.	D9.6	Done
The pilot must list the personal data harvesting tools which will be used and confirm for each of them whether their policies comply with GDPR requirements.	D9.7	Done
A description of the security measures that will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to personal data or the equipment used for processing must be submitted.	D9.8	Done
The pilot must evaluate the ethics risks related to the data processing activities of the project. This includes also an opinion if data protection impact assessment should be conducted under art.35 General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679. The risk evaluation and the opinion must be submitted.	D9.9	Done

Conclusions

To sum up, the current deliverable is a part of the WP6 that is pilot's work package dedicated to deploying, validating and evaluating the pilot systems with the active involvement of the public authorities of the consortium. More specifically, the current deliverable (D6.1 Pilot Sites Preparation and Transformation) focuses on the first objective of the WP6 that is to analyse the activities that the pilots need to carry out for the deployment and operation of the project's pilot systems at the 5 pilot sites.

To begin with, the preparation and transformation plan and its main required activities have been analysed. More specifically, the pilots were requested to provide us with the necessary details on the HW/SW needed for raw data collection. As it has been seen, while some of the pilots will take advantage of the deployment of sensors to acquire raw data, others will solely rely on their current data providers.

To continue, the present document also describes the infrastructure the pilots needed to provide the implementation teams with real-time datasets. In most of the cases, pilots will use equipment like local servers to store data that will be then integrated into AI4PP, or they will provide APIs that can be used by the project's central collection systems.

Lastly, in terms of HW/SW infrastructure, pilots provide us with more information needed to access the pilot UI and algorithms via the VPME component. As it has been seen, for ensuring their access pilots have already a plan to use personal computers and dedicated working stations.

However, apart from the necessary HW/SW in the course of this deliverable, pilots need to provide historical data for each of the datasets as defined in the D2.3, where applicable, and to also describe the process for making these historical pilot datasets accessible to the implementation team.

Moreover, pilots need to investigate and decide whether local legacy systems that are already in place and in use need to be integrated with the AI4PP pilot implementations, in the course of this project. Based on the feedback received, it is the case that some of the pilots do not support any legacy systems that require integrations, while others use some of this kind of system that might need to be integrated. In the latter case, these integrations will be further discussed at a later stage of the project.

Equally important, to complete their preparation and transformation plan pilots requested to create a very initial plan of the stakeholders that will be involved in the AI4PP project. In more details, pilots needed to identify the main stakeholders involved in their pilot, mapping and prioritising them based on the level of their involvement and provide us with details related to their training. Leveraging the prioritised use cases, all pilots have already a concrete plan of the main stakeholders that need to be mobilised throughout the project.

Last but not least, pilots had to provide us with a status on the fulfilment of the required ethical activities as they are specified in the deliverables of WP9.

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